

Spectral and Polarographic Behaviour of Ternary Complexes of Copper(II)-Glycylglycine and Some Amino-acids

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The mixed ligand complexes of the type $[\text{CuAB}]X \text{H}_2\text{O}$, (where $X = 0$ or 2 , A = amide deprotonated glycylglycine, B = glycine, alanine, serine, threonine or valine) have been isolated. The formulae of these complexes have been proposed on the basis of elemental analyses. Coordination through amino group of glycylglycine and secondary ligands, deprotonated amide group of glycylglycine and carboxylate group of the amino acids have been investigated on the basis of ir data. Visible spectral studies made on these complexes lead to the conclusion that these are of tetragonally distorted octahedral geometry in aqueous solutions.

Polarographic behaviour of the complexes have been investigated in $0.1 M$ aqueous sodium perchlorate medium. Polarographic characteristics ($E_{1/2}$, i_d , D , slope, α) have been determined. Activation energy of diffusion Q_D has been calculated by Vlček's equation. Values of reference rate constant, K_r , at a reference potential $-0.3 V$ against SCE have been determined from the characteristics of irreversible waves. The mechanism of electroreduction of the complexes $[\text{Cu}(\text{gg})(\text{val})] 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{gg})(\text{ser})] 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ undergoes change with temperature at dropping mercury electrode. A correlation between spectral parameters, ν_{max} , and polarographic parameters ($E_{1/2}$, K_r , Q_D), has been made and anomalies observed have been explained on the basis of steric effects. The data have been rationalized by proposing a mechanism of the electroreduction of the depolariser at the electrode surface on basis of the orientation of the orbitals of the central metal ion and its local symmetry, D_{2h} .

It is being increasingly realized that the transition metal complexes behave characteristically at the dropping mercury electrode and yield information about the lowest vacant orbital. Considering the information about the highest occupied orbital from spectral behaviour of such a system, it would be possible to correlate redox properties of coordination compounds with their spectral parameters. Following this idea, attempts¹⁻⁸ have been made to seek correlation of the spectral behaviour *vis-a-vis* electrode characteristics of coordination compounds with some success. The report on ternary complexes, however, is very scanty. In the present communication, such a correlation has been attempted by studying electrode behaviour of some ternary complexes of a biologically important transition metal like copper and biologically important ligands such as glycylglycine as primary ligand and some amino-acids as secondary ligands. Such ternary complexes are important in transport of copper through biological membranes. The complexes studied are $[\text{CuAB}]X \text{H}_2\text{O}$, where $X = 0$ or 2 , A = amide deprotonated glycylglycine, and B = glycine, alanine, serine, threonine or valine.

Equilibrium studies of these complexes have been made by previous workers⁹⁻¹² potentiometrically and conclusions have been drawn, concerning the linkages of amino-acids and of glycylglycine to copper(II) ion on the basis of stability constants. No attempt, to the best of the authors' knowledge, has been made to isolate and characterize these complexes. The authors have, therefore, attempted to isolate and characterize $[\text{CuAB}]X \text{H}_2\text{O}$ complexes. The formulae of the complexes have been proposed on the basis of elemental analysis. Infrared and electronic spectral studies revealed these complexes to be of tetragonally distorted octahedral structure in aqueous solutions. A comparison of their redox properties with the spectral parameters has been made. A probable mechanism have been proposed for the reduction of these complexes at electrode surface on the basis of their orientation at the electrode surface and their D_{2h} symmetry.

Experimental

All the complexes were prepared by heating the mixture of an equimolar aqueous solutions of

AnalaR glycylglycine and any one of the secondary ligands, *i.e.* glycine, alanine, serine, threonine and valine with an excess of freshly precipitated copper hydroxide on water bath for 0.5 h. Hot solutions were filtered and concentrated to one-third of its volume. Absolute alcohol was added to the hot solution to get precipitates of the complexes. Precipitates were washed with absolute alcohol and solvent ether. All complexes were dried at 50° and are intense blue in colour. All of the complexes are highly soluble in water and are insoluble in organic solvents like ethanol, benzene and ether.

Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen in the complexes were estimated by G.D.R. microanalyser. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 377. Electronic spectra of all the complexes were taken in aqueous solution on Beckman 26 spectrophotometer.

For polarographic investigations AnalaR sodium perchlorate was used as a supporting electrolyte. To remove the oxygen from polarographic solution, purified nitrogen gas was bubbled at the rate of two bubbles per sec for 0.5 h. All the polarograms were recorded with the help of a manual polarographic circuit as recommended by Kolthoff and Lingane. All the potentials were measured against Hume and Harris saturated calomel electrode. The cell resistance was measured with the help of an a.c. Wheatstone bridge and was found to be $1000 \pm 100 \Omega$. Therefore, ir correction was not needed. The characteristics of dropping mercury electrode were determined at three different heights of mercury column, one set of data is as follows (Table-2): $h_{0.01r} = 58.5$ cm, $t = 3.8$ sec, $m = 1.5$ mg/sec, $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 1.64$.

Results and Discussion

On the basis of the carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen estimation (Table 1) formulae proposed for the complexes studied are, (I) [Cu(gg)(thr)] $2H_2O$, (II) [Cu(gg)(alan)] $2H_2O$, (III) [Cu(gg)(val)] $2H_2O$, (IV) [Cu(gg)(gly)], (V) [Cu(gg)(ser)] $2H_2O$; where gg=glycylglycine, thr=threonine, alan=alanine, val=valine, gly=glycine, ser=serine.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES OF COPPER(II)—GLYCYLGLYCINE AND SOME AMINO-ACIDS

No.	Complex	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd)		
		C	H	N
I.	[Cu(gg)(thr)] $2H_2O$	27.52 (27.86)	5.40 (5.45)	11.95 (12.07)
II.	[Cu(gg)(alan)] $2H_2O$	27.20 (27.27)	5.22 (5.52)	13.50 (13.63)
III.	[Cu(gg)(val)] $2H_2O$	31.52 (31.21)	6.20 (6.07)	12.00 (12.14)
IV.	[Cu(gg)(gly)]	27.02 (26.80)	4.52 (4.09)	15.50 (15.63)
V.	[Cu(gg)(ser)] $2H_2O$	25.80 (25.15)	5.00 (5.09)	12.25 (12.57)

Infrared spectra: Peptides¹³ of low molecular weight and amino-acids¹⁴ exist as Zwitterions with an open chain structure. In the ir spectra of the amino-acids and glycylglycine used, the bands at 3070, 2564, 2100, and 1630 cm^{-1} are due to the presence of $-NH_3^+$ group¹⁵. These bands are found to be absent in the complexes under investigation and two bands appearing at ~ 3320 and 3240 cm^{-1} lead to the conclusion that there is coordination¹⁶ through the amino group of the glycylglycine and amino-acids used in all the cases. The carbonyl group of the peptide link absorbs¹⁷ at 1670 and 1540 cm^{-1} in glycylglycine. These bands shift to 1600 and 1535 cm^{-1} , respectively in case of the complexes. This shows that there is coordination through N atom of the deprotonated amide group of the glycylglycine¹⁷. It is also observed that there is shift in the asymmetric and symmetric stretching frequencies of the carboxylate group of amino-acids and follows Nakamoto's order¹⁸ (asymmetric stretching frequencies increase while symmetric stretching frequencies decrease due to coordination), indicating that there is coordination through carboxylate group of the amino acids. Two new bands appear for all the complexes at 435 and 535 cm^{-1} which may be due to Cu-O bond¹⁹ and C-N bond¹⁹, respectively. The difference in asymmetric and symmetric stretching frequencies of the carboxylate group provides a clue that Cu-O bond is ionic²⁰ in nature.

Electronic spectra: All the complexes give a single asymmetric absorption band at ~ 16000 cm^{-1} ($\epsilon \sim 200$), which shows that these complexes are of tetragonally distorted octahedral geometry^{11,21}.

Polarographic investigations: Electroreduction of the complexes investigated is found to be a single step, two electron, irreversible reduction at the dropping mercury electrode (dme). The values of $i_d/\sqrt{h_{0.01r}}$ for all the complexes under study are almost constant for three different heights of the mercury column. This confirms that the limiting current for all the processes of electroreduction are diffusion-controlled.

The slopes of the plot of $-E$ vs $\log(i_d - i)/i$ for the current potential curves have been used as a criterion for reversibility. Slope values observed for all the complexes are found to be greater than the theoretical values at all the temperature and thus exhibiting that the process of electroreduction is irreversible. The transfer coefficient, α , and the half wave potential, $E_{1/2}$, have been determined from Oldham and Parry's method²². For the comparison of the rate of electron transfer of all the complexes, rate constant, K_r , has been calculated at -0.30 V against SCE, which is more useful than comparison of rate constants at formal potentials²³, using the following equation

$$E_{1/2} = E_r + \frac{2.303 RT}{\alpha nF} \log 0.89 Kr \sqrt{t/D}$$

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES OF COPPER(II)-GLYCYLGLYCINE AND SOME AMINO-ACIDS IN AQUEOUS 0.1 M SODIUM PERCHLORATE MEDIUM

$h_{\text{c o o r}} = 58.5 \text{ cm}, [\text{Depolariser}] = 10^{-3} \text{ M}, [\text{Triton X-100}] = 0.001 \%$

Complex no.	Temp. °C	i_d μA	$-E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ V	Slope V	α	$D^{\frac{1}{2}} \times 10^3$ $\text{cm}^2 \text{sec}^{-1}$	$k_r \times 10^3$ cm sec^{-1}	Q_D kcal mol ⁻¹
I	25	8.23	0.278	0.20	0.15	4.14	3.07	3.8
	35	9.22	0.275	0.23	0.14	4.64	3.48	
	45	10.35	0.274	0.24	0.13	5.21	3.89	
	55	10.69	0.269	0.25	0.13	5.39	4.23	
II	25	9.05	0.276	0.22	0.14	4.50	3.38	3.5
	35	9.61	0.272	0.22	0.14	4.84	3.77	
	45	10.64	0.269	0.25	0.13	5.36	4.22	
	55	11.84	0.264	0.27	0.12	5.96	4.82	
III	25	9.26	0.290	0.22	0.14	4.61	2.96	3.6
	35	10.29	0.284	0.24	0.12	5.18	3.49	
	45	11.00	0.282	0.26	0.12	5.54	3.75	
	55	11.79	0.275	0.27	0.12	5.93	4.32	
IV	25	7.88	0.272	0.24	0.12	3.97	3.00	3.5
	35	8.85	0.270	0.22	0.14	4.47	3.55	
	45	9.77	0.269	0.28	0.11	4.88	3.76	
	55	10.42	0.267	0.28	0.11	5.27	4.11	
V	25	8.16	0.257	0.21	0.14	4.11	3.75	3.4
	35	9.58	0.256	0.24	0.13	4.82	4.29	
	45	10.72	0.255	0.26	0.12	5.40	4.73	
	55	11.43	0.247	0.26	0.12	5.75	5.58	

where all the terms have their usual significance.

The values of i_d , at different temperatures have been used to calculate the activation energy of diffusion, Q_D , by Vlček's equation²⁴

$$\log \frac{i_d}{m^{2/3} t^{1/6}} = \log 0.627 n F C D^{\frac{1}{2}} - \frac{1/2 Q_D}{2.3 RT}$$

The polarographic characteristics of all the complexes at different temperatures have been given in Table 2. The perusal of the results shows that the values of i_d increase with the rise in temperature for all the complexes, which may be due to the increased concentration of the depolariser at the electrode surface with increasing temperature. For all the complexes $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ goes on decreasing, i.e. shifts towards more positive potential, with the rise of temperature, showing easier reduction may be attributed to (a) the increase of energy of the electrons in the electrode, which will reach fermi level²⁵ easily, and (b) the easier availability²⁶ of the vacant orbital in the depolariser. The graph plotted temp. vs $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ for the complexes I, II and IV is a straight line showing that the mechanism²⁵ of electroreduction for these complexes do not change with temperature, while for complexes III and V these plots are nonlinear, which indicates that the mechanism²⁵ of electroreduction for these two complexes varies with temperature.

For the sake of comparison of polarographic behaviour with spectral behaviour, the polarographic characteristics ($E_{\frac{1}{2}}$, K_r) and the corresponding spectral parameter, ν_{max} , are given in

Table 3. On the basis of ν_{max} values the strength of the ligands should be in the order thr > alan > gly ~ ser ~ val

TABLE 3—SPECTRAL AND POLAROGRAPHIC PARAMETERS OF THE MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES OF COPPER(II) WITH GLYCYLGLYCINE AND SOME AMINO-ACIDS AT 25 ± 0.2°

Complex no.	$-E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ V	$K_r \times 10^3$ cm sec^{-1}	ν_{max} cm^{-1}
I	0.278	3.07	15870
II	0.276	3.38	15820
III	0.290	2.96	15750
IV	0.272	3.00	15750
V	0.257	3.75	15750

Hence, one would expect that the values of half wave potential should be in the order^{25, 26}

thr > alan > gly ~ ser ~ val

provided no non-structural factor plays any part. But the perusal of Table 3 reveals that the electroreduction of III is the most difficult one. These anomalous observations may be rationalized by assuming that each of the complex orients at the electrode surface such that the (gg) ligand lies away from the electrode and the other ligand lies towards the electrode surface. On the basis of the steric effects, one would expect the values of the half wave potential to be in the order

val > thr > alan > ser > gly

Table 3 shows that this order is obeyed by all the complexes except glycine complex as the $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ for complex IV is greater than that for V. The

electrocapillary curves for these complexes show that only the complex of serine and that of glycine adsorb at the electrode surface, which leads to the conclusion that the $E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ of these two complexes should decrease, but it does not give any hint as to why serine complex is reduced easily. Most probably, the presence of —OH group in the serine ligand makes the reduction easier due to its electron withdrawing nature.

This observation can be further rationalized by considering a proper symmetry of the depolariser and its orientation at the electrode surface. As has been reported earlier¹¹ and on the basis of ν_{max} and ϵ values, these complexes are of tetragonally distorted octahedral geometry, hence the local symmetry of copper(II) ion in the solution may be assumed to be D_{2h} . In this symmetry, the splitting of the five d orbitals of copper(II) ion is such that the energy of the orbitals is in the order

$$d_{xz}, d_{yz} < d_{z^2} < d_{xy} < d_{x^2-y^2}$$

Therefore the accommodation of nine electrons in different 3d orbitals would be as follows

$$(d_{xz})^2 (d_{yz})^2 (d_{z^2})^2 (d_{xy})^2 (d_{x^2-y^2})^1$$

Considering that the orientation of the complex particle is such that the xz plane (or yz plane) is perpendicular to the electrode surface, the d_{z^2} and also the d_{xz} (or d_{yz}) orbital point towards the electrode. The two incoming electrons needed for electroreduction should be accommodated in the lowest lying vacant orbital, $d_{x^2-y^2}$ in the present case. But this orbital is incapable of receiving the electrons due to its very low electron affinity and unfavourable orientation. Out of the two suitably oriented orbitals, namely d_{z^2} and d_{xz} (or d_{yz}), the later is low lying and hence it must be vacated prior to the electron transfer proper. The two electrons of this orbital are promoted under the strong influence of the electrode field to the next higher vacant orbitals, thus enabling d_{xz} (or d_{yz}) orbital to function as redox orbital. The promotion energy required for this process would depend upon the energy difference between the non-bonding e_g (d_{xz} , d_{yz}) orbitals and the anti-bonding b_{1g}^* and a_{1g}^* orbitals, which also depend on the ligand field strength and hence the case of electroreduction of the depolariser may be correlated with ligand field strength as has been observed (Table 3).

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References

1. V. SRIVASTAVA, K. B. LAL and H. L. NIGAM, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 59, 497.
2. D. BANERJEA and P. BANERJEA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 1321.
3. A. A. VLČEK, *Rev. Chim. Miner.*, 1968, 15, 299.
4. J. MASEK, *Inorg. Chim. Acta Rev.*, 1969, 3, 99.
5. H. S. SHARMA and H. L. NIGAM, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, 14, 410.
6. A. A. VLČEK, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1968, 13, 1063.
7. G. SHIVON, S. ZEECHIN and G. PILLONI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, 39, 115.
8. S. N. MANDLOI, P. K. CHITALE and M. S. VERMA, *Vijnan Parishad Anusandhan Patrika*, 1982, 25, 389.
9. M. S. BALKRISHNAN, P. NATARAJAN and M. SANTAPPA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1975, 44, 303.
10. R. P. MARTIN and L. MOSSONI, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1971, 246, 5944.
11. I. NAGYPAL and A. GERGELY, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1977, 1109.
12. H. SIGEL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1975, 14, 1535.
13. E. W. HUGHES and W. J. MOORE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 2618.
14. H. W. THOMPSON, D. L. NICHOLSON and L. N. SHORT, *Faraday Discuss. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 9, 222.
15. R. J. KOGEL, J. P. GREENSTEIN, M. WINITZ, S. M. BIRNBAUM and R. A. MCCALLUM, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 5708.
16. J. A. KIEFF and K. NAKAMOTO, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1961, 292, 2561.
17. M. K. KIM and A. E. MARTEEL, *Biochemistry*, 1964, 3, 1169.
18. K. NAKAMOTO, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 83, 4528.
19. C. R. SAXENA, Ph.D. Thesis, Vikram University, 1978.
20. D. SAWYER and P. PAULSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 1597.
21. N. S. GILL and R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 1977.
22. K. B. OLDHAM and E. P. PARRY, *Anal. Chem.*, 1968, 40, 65.
23. A. A. VLČEK, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 5, 211.
24. A. A. VLČEK, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1959, 24, 3538.
25. J. O'M, BOKRIS, *J. Chem. Educat.*, 1971, 48, 352.
26. S. S. SINGH, M. S. VERMA and H. L. NIGAM, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1978, 23, 1287.